

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

WP5 – Development of the hackAIR platform

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Table of Contents

Glossary	5
1 Executive Summary	6
2 Introduction.....	6
2.1 Development Methodology.....	6
2.2 Integrations	7
2.3 Testing	7
2.4 Open source	9
2.5 Gamification	9
2.6 Mobile Releases.....	10
3 hackAIR Platform architecture.....	10
4 Platform functionality.....	12
4.1 Web Application	13
Non-registered users	13
Registered users	14
4.2 Mobile Application.....	22
Non-registered users	22
Registered users	23
5 Difficulties faced & lessons learnt.....	27
References.....	29

Table of Figures

Figure 1 Development Task list in JIRA (active sprint issues)	7
Figure 2 Pie chart presenting the type of issues reported.....	8
Figure 3 Pie chart presenting the status of issues reported	9
Figure 4 Releases of the mobile apps	10
Figure 5 hackAIR integrated platform.....	11
Figure 6: Home screen for non-registered users	13
Figure 7: Home screen with selection of a specific city for non-registered users	14
Figure 8: The hackAIR air quality index (source: hackAIR website).....	14
Figure 9: Registration form.....	15
Figure 10: Profile section.....	16
Figure 11: Home screen for registered users	17
Figure 12: Profile - Overview of contributions.....	17

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

Figure 13: Profile - Badges	18
Figure 14: Profile - Photos	19
Figure 15: Profile - Perceptions	19
Figure 16: Profile - Sensors overview.....	20
Figure 17: Adding a new sensor.....	20
Figure 18: Latest measurements of a specific sensor	21
Figure 19: Profile – Followers	21
Figure 20: Social tab	22
Figure 21: Uploading a sky photo for non-registered users.....	22
Figure 22: Home page - mobile	23
Figure 23: Historical data - mobile.....	23
Figure 24: Take a photo functionality - Mobile.....	24
Figure 25: Submit perception functionality - Mobile	24
Figure 26: Air quality map - Mobile	25
Figure 27: Profile overview - Mobile.....	26
Figure 28: Connection with hackAIR mobile sensor - Mobile	27

Glossary

Abbreviation/Acronym	Meaning
API	Application Programming Interface
COTS	Commercial off-the-shelf
REST	REpresentational State Transfer
R/G	Red / Green
G/B	Green / Blue
UTC	Universal Time Coordinated

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable summarizes the updates on the hackAIR platform and the integration plan that were essential during the pilot execution of the project. Furthermore, it covers any additional functionality and change performed due to issues / events happened and influenced the hackAIR workflow.

Chapter 2 describes changes to the tools and the development methodology, the integration and testing strategy and, the release of the platform codes.

Chapter 3 presents the final architecture of the hackAIR platform after describing the latest updates that were made in the architecture since D5.1 and D5.2.

Chapter 4 describes the functionality of the final hackAIR application.

Chapter 5 presents some of the difficulties faced during the development of the platform along with the actions taken in order to tackle them. These could serve as valuable lessons learnt that may be considered in future projects similar to hackAIR.

2 Introduction

2.1 Development Methodology

The development team continued following the SCRUM agile methodology until the development of the final hackAIR open platform, as specified in D5.2, however PivotalTracker¹, which was used as the development project management tool, was replaced with JIRA². JIRA is also based on agile methodologies including SCRUM and was chosen since it provides a cleaner user interface and more useful features in comparison to PivotalTracker. Jira was also integrated with an easy to use issue tracking system (JIRA ServiceDesk) that was the tool where all the hackAIR partners requested assistance or reported bugs to the DRAXIS development team.

Also, although in the beginning of the development the duration of each sprint³ was bi-weekly, in the last semester the project partners decided to change this plan to monthly sprints since most of the platform features had been delivered and any remaining issues mostly concerned improvements and bug fixes.

¹ <https://www.pivotaltracker.com/dashboard>

² <https://www.atlassian.com/software/jira>

³ sprint is a term used in scrum to define iterations in the development process

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

Figure 1 Development Task list in JIRA (active sprint issues)

2.2 Integrations

As it was described in D5.1 (Architecture and integration framework definition specification) and D5.2 (1st version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform), the following modules were integrated into the hackAIR open platform:

- Social Media Mining (responsible to crawl sky photos from social networks and web cameras)
- Open Data Crawling (responsible to crawl sensor measurements from web portals or services) (deliverable D3.2)
- Image Analysis (responsible to analyze sky or cardboard photos, detect areas containing sky and provide useful information that can be used to identify the air pollution levels, such as whether sky was detected / is usable, R/G and G/B ratios etc.) (deliverable D3.4)
- Recommendations and Decision Support (responsible to provide recommendations to individuals based on the air pollution levels in their area and their personal profile) (deliverable D4.2)
- Data Fusion (responsible to combine the air pollution information from all the available sources in a single map layer) (deliverable D4.1)
- Gamification and Reputation System (the mechanism to engage more users in the platform)

Additionally, a timezone service was developed and integrated to the platform to handle conversions between different timezones, essential to convert the timestamp of Flickr photos from local timezone to UTC timezone. The service was developed to use a third-party API, TimezoneDB API⁴.

2.3 Testing

Following up on D5.2 (1st version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform), the test scenarios were run in multiple iterations (both automated and manual tests) before each release of the platform. The results from the tests

⁴ <https://timezonedb.com/>

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

were documented and in case of failure, issue reports were created in the project management tool that had to be resolved by the development team (some statistics are presented at the end of this section). When a release of the platform proved to have bugs and depending on the severity of the issue, the development team would work to correct the problems and for some cases extend the testing scenarios to cover also the new cases.

Regarding the development of the mobile apps, the development team faced a number of issues that concerned different mobile devices and operating systems. In order to easily identify the issues found along with information about the environment where each of them was captured, the team used a third-party crash reporting solution, Crashlytics⁵. Crashlytics provides detailed and actionable insights regarding app crashes, such as the device model, operating system etc. along with useful debugging information (such as the exact line of code where the app crashed).

After the identification of app crashes, the development team had to reproduce those issues and provide cross-platform resolutions. To simulate different mobile environments, the team used the official emulators provided for both Android and iOS. However, some issues were related to specific mobile-device capabilities (such as the camera and GPS), that cannot be simulated by the emulators, so the development team had to create a group of internal testers that would be able to test the apps on physical mobile devices. The team documented all mobile devices that were already available and obtained additional models that did not already exist. Before each new release to the app stores, the internal testers had to thoroughly test the mobile apps and after all features were tested and fixed the apps were made publicly available to the application stores.

Regarding the issues reported and handled in JIRA, some statistics based on type, priority and status are provided below. The most common reported issues were bugs representing the 40% of the total issues (476). Since the 1st version of the hackAIR platform was used during the pilot phase, this number is quite reasonable. The rest of issues reported concerned tasks and user stories (enhancements, new features etc.).

Figure 2 Pie chart presenting the type of issues reported

The vast majority of the reported issues (97% of the total issues) have been already resolved by the development team, the 2% of them is currently being tested and only the 1% of them still remains on the team's task list. The project

⁵ <http://try.crashlytics.com/>

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

partners will continue to report issues identified by the pilot users until the end of the project, while the development team will prioritize them depending on their severity and solve them.

Figure 3 Pie chart presenting the status of issues reported

2.4 Open source

Following the open mentality of the project, the hackAIR platform is open source and has been published to Github and Zenodo repositories under APGL v3 license⁶.

The platform is available on GitHub under the hackair-project organization:

<https://github.com/hackair-project>

The individual repositories for the API and web/mobile apps can be found at:

- **hackAIR web app:** <https://github.com/hackair-project/hackair-web>
- **hackAIR mobile:** <https://github.com/hackair-project/hackair-mobile>
- **hackAIR API:** <https://github.com/hackair-project/hackair-api>

The above repositories have also been published on Zenodo and are available at the following url:

<https://zenodo.org/record/1434702>

2.5 Gamification

The initial plan for gamification was to start small with only basic features and then choose which features to implement from the ones we collected during the requirements phase and reported in D5.2. It seemed early from the start that the gamification features were functioning to their purpose, as the applications reached very soon their targets on user retention (number of photos contributed, number of sensors created). However, gamification didn't

⁶ <https://www.gnu.org/licenses/agpl-3.0.en.html>

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

help in new users' acquisition, thus the partners agreed to focus on other features of the platform that had greater potential to attract new users.

The gamification features that were available at the first release of the hackAIR platform:

- User profile with points. Users can earn points by completing specific actions such as complete onboarding, login for the first time etc. The points earned are visible in the user's profile.
- Basic badges on the user profile. Users can also acquire badges by performing specific one-time or recurring actions. For example, a user can win the "A health watcher!" badge by adding to their profile the health groups they belong to.
- Assign badges on creation of a new sensor. When users manage to connect a sensor successfully for the first time, they win the "A hacker's masterpiece" badge.

The additional gamification features developed during the pilot phase were the following:

- Users can see the badges that other users have on their profile.
- A screen was developed with all the badges showing as "inactive" the ones that the user has still not won.
- Addition of badges that are awarded on different actions (e.g. spend 1 hour in the app, login three days in a row, upload photos from at least 5 different locations etc.).

2.6 Mobile Releases

Since the beginning of the project, the development team provided multiple releases of the mobile app for the Android and iOS platforms, both on recurring pre-defined intervals (at the end of each sprint) but also ad-hoc, when issues came up that were evaluated as important. The tech team provided ongoing support to solve any upcoming issues, such as changes in third-party libraries used, bug fixes etc.

An overview can be seen below:

	Android	iOS
Number of releases	15	20
Latest release	5.6.1	5.6.1
Latest release date	10/10/18	12/10/18

Figure 4 Releases of the mobile apps

New updated versions of the mobile app are expected to be released by the end of the project.

3 hackAIR Platform architecture

The hackAIR platform architecture was described in D5.1 and was followed, with some additions and changes described in D5.2 and some final few changes that are described in this section. A diagram of the final architecture can be seen in Figure 5.

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

Figure 5 hackAIR integrated platform

The changes in the architecture of the platform are summarized below:

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

- Nginx server was added on top of all modules in the business logic layer to act as a reverse proxy. All requests coming to the web server hosting the platform have to pass through the nginx proxy server first. Depending on the proxy's settings, each request can be allowed or denied. If the request is allowed, then the proxy forwards it to the respective module that is responsible for handling the request. To decide on the proxy that will be used for this purpose the development team compared different solutions (nginx and apache server) and chose to use nginx since it is much faster in serving static content and also more convenient to configure as a reverse proxy.
- The Text mining module was removed since it was decided that this functionality could not be supported.
- The Problem Description Language module was integrated into the Recommendations & Decision Support module, since this was the only module that needed to communicate with it and the integration of the two would allow for better and faster communication with the apps.

4 Platform functionality

The web platform can be found at: <https://platform.hackair.eu/>

The mobile applications can be downloaded from:

<https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=gr.draxis.hackair&hl=en> (Google play store)

<https://itunes.apple.com/us/app/hackair/id1337710268?mt=8> (App store)

The web and mobile app functionalities are presented below.

4.1 Web Application

Non-registered users

When users enter the web hackAIR platform they can choose or search the city for which they want to see air quality information (Figure 6). For example (Figure 7) by choosing a city from the drop-down list, non-registered users are able

Figure 6: Home screen for non-registered users

to see all the air quality data collected for this location choosing the respective layers on the right side of the map. Specifically:

- Measurements from the hackAIR DIY sensors
- Air quality estimations from the hackAIR cardboards
- Measurements from the Luftdaten DIY sensors
- Air quality estimations from sky photos
- Measurements from official ground-based stations
- Perceptions of the quality of the air from the hackAIR mobile app users
- Continuous air quality maps.

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

Figure 7: Home screen with selection of a specific city for non-registered users

The color scale indicates the air quality conditions with different colors. In addition, users can see the characterization of the air quality based on the hackAIR air quality index (Figure 8).

HOW DO YOU DETERMINE THE AIR QUALITY RATINGS (BAD, MEDIUM, GOOD)?

hackAIR deals with point measurements for particulate matter pollution from a variety of sources and in different units of measurements. As this can get very complicated, we use an internal index to be able to compare and display measurements consistently. On the platform, you will often see ratings like bad, medium, good. These ratings translate to actual measurements as follows:

Rating	AOD scale (for image analysis)	PM10 scale ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	PM2.5 scale ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	Blobs detected (hackAIR cardboard)	hAQI index (from data fusion)
Very Good	≥ 0 and $\leq 0,14$	≥ 0 and ≤ 20	≥ 0 and ≤ 10	≥ 0 and ≤ 1500	≥ 0 and ≤ 1.5
Good	$> 0,14$ and $\leq 0,34$	> 20 and ≤ 50	> 10 and ≤ 25	> 1500 and ≤ 2500	> 1.5 and ≤ 2.5
Medium	$> 0,34$ and $\leq 0,44$	> 50 and ≤ 70	> 25 and ≤ 35	> 2500 and ≤ 3500	> 2.5 and ≤ 3.5
Bad	$> 0,44$	> 70	> 35	> 3500	> 3.5

3 Technical support

Figure 8: The hackAIR air quality index (source: hackAIR website)

On the home page, non-registered users can also see general information about hackAIR and the data that it collects. On the footer there is the “share feedback” option, which users can choose to send their opinion about hackAIR.

On the upper right side of the screen, four options are provided to users:

- “About” tab provides general information about hackAIR.
- “Explore” tab presents the map with the sensors and measurements. Users can also choose which sensors, photos, stations and perceptions they want to see using the map filters.
- “Login” tab may be used to register or login to hackAIR.
- Users are also able to change the “Language” of the platform.

Registered users

Registration

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

The screenshot shows the hackAIR registration form. At the top left is the hackAIR logo and a search bar. At the top right are links for 'About', 'Explore', 'Login', and 'en'. The main content area is a white registration form with the title 'Register using your email'. It includes a caution message: 'Caution: Your username will be public. Consider not including personal information'. There are four input fields: 'Email', 'Password', and 'Repeat your password'. Below the fields are two checkboxes: 'I want to receive newsletters' and 'By registering to hackAIR you accept our terms of service'. A 'REGISTER' button is at the bottom right of the form.

Figure 9: Registration form

Users who want to have full access to the hackAIR features should register by completing the form presented in Figure 9, and by accepting the hackAIR terms of use. In addition, users can give their permission so that hackAIR sends them the project's newsletters, while only in the German version of the platform users can additionally choose if they want to receive newsletters from BUND. After completing this form, users receive a confirmation e-mail with instructions that they should follow to activate their account.

Profile- Edit

After logging in users can enter the hackAIR platform and fill in their profile by selecting their profile picture on the upper right corner of the screen, click on the "Profile" option from the menu that shows up and then click on the "Edit" button. Filling in their profile allows users to receive more personalized air quality information. They can optionally fill in their "Town/City", "Year of birth", "Gender" and "Language". They can also choose for which sensitivities and outdoor activities they want to receive personalized recommendations on the home screen. Users can also choose to create a secondary profile for another person for which they want to receive personalized recommendations, by filling in the second form with information about this person.

On the same screen, they can also choose if they want their profile to be public and reachable from other hackAIR users, or private ("Make my profile public" option).

On the same screen, users can change their password, change their privacy settings, and delete their account.

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

The screenshot displays the 'Edit profile' interface on the hackAIR platform. The top navigation bar includes 'Dashboard', 'Social', and a user profile icon. The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column shows a user profile card with a profile picture, the name 'hackAIR Agent', '1350 points', and location 'Berlin, DE'. Below this are sections for 'Private info' (Age: 29, Groups: Respiratory diseases, Gender: female, and selected outdoor activities: Walking, Running, Outdoor job, Eating outside) and 'Communities' (Make my profile public: checked). The right column is the 'Edit profile' form, which includes a 'Username' field with a warning: 'Caution: Your username will be public. Consider not including personal information'. The form is organized into two sections: 'PERSONAL INFORMATION' and 'SECONDARY PROFILE INFORMATION'. The 'PERSONAL INFORMATION' section includes fields for Town/City (Berlin, DE), Year of birth (1989), Gender (Female), and Language (English). It also features checkboxes for 'I would like to receive information about the following sensitivities' (Respiratory diseases) and 'I would like to receive information about the following outdoor activities' (Walking, Eating outside, Running, Outdoor job). The 'SECONDARY PROFILE INFORMATION' section includes fields for Year of birth (1995), Gender (Female), and checkboxes for 'I would like to receive information about the following sensitivities' (Respiratory diseases) and 'I would like to receive information about the following outdoor activities' (Walking, Running). At the bottom of the form, there is a checkbox for 'I want a secondary profile' (checked) and 'CANCEL' and 'SAVE' buttons.

Figure 10: Profile section

Home page

After completing their profile, users can select the “Dashboard” tab and return to the home screen so that they see personalized air quality information for the city of their interest. As the non-registered users, a registered user can see various air quality information on the map, plus measurements from their own sensors and air quality estimations from sky photos that they have uploaded via the hackAIR mobile app. On the left side of the screen they can see some personalized recommendation for the outdoor activities they selected in their profile and according to their sensitivities and the current air pollution levels. Accordingly, they receive personalized recommendations for the secondary profile, while in the yellow bulb they can see tips on how they can improve the air quality in their location (e.g. “You can always improve the air by using public transport”). On the second half of the page users can see a graph with historical air quality data for selected city for the last week, month, or year.

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

Figure 11: Home screen for registered users

Profile – Overview

By choosing again the “Profile” tab, users can see an overview of their latest contributions to hackAIR, such as measurements from sensors that they have set up, and sky photos that they have uploaded on the hackAIR mobile app (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Profile - Overview of contributions

On the same page, on the tab “Achievements” users can see the badges that they have gained so far through the gamification missions of hackAIR along with the badges that remain to be unlocked (Figure 13). Users can earn badges by completing specific actions in hackAIR, such as completing their profile, uploading a sky photo or installing a new

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

sensor. When users click on a badge, a pop-up window appears that shows the name of the badge, a short explanation of what users need to do to unlock it and a link to share their achievement on social media.

Figure 13: Profile - Badges

On the tab “Photos”, users are able to see a list of the photos they have uploaded on the hackAIR mobile application, and specifically sky photos and photos of their cardboard sensors (<http://www.hackair.eu/hackair-cardboard/>). Sky photos that were used by hackAIR for the estimation of air quality are marked with a check-mark icon . By choosing a sky photo, users can see the air quality characterization according to this photo or why the photo was not used (Figure 14).

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

Figure 14: Profile - Photos

On the tab “Perceptions”, users can have an overview of the perception on the air quality that they have submitted via the hackAIR mobile application.

Figure 15: Profile - Perceptions

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

On the tab “Sensors”, users see a map displaying all the hackAIR sensors they have set up, along with a list of these sensors, their names, their unique IDs, and their latest information.

Figure 16: Profile - Sensors overview

By choosing to add a new sensor, users are requested to fill in the following form (Figure 17) in order to acquire the unique sensor access key and complete the sensor set up as described in the relevant tutorials (<http://www.hackair.eu/hackair-home-v2/>, <http://www.hackair.eu/hackair-mobile/>).

Edit

First name*	PSoC sensor_centre
Sensor type*	hackAIR home
Location	<input type="text"/>
Location details	<input type="text"/>
Floor	<input type="text"/>

Figure 17: Adding a new sensor

Users can also select a specific sensor to see its latest measurements and export them in CSV files.

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

Figure 18: Latest measurements of a specific sensor

Finally, under the tab “Followers”, users can have an overview of the other hackAIR users who follow them, and follow them back.

Figure 19: Profile – Followers

Social tab

By selecting the social tab on the upper right corner of the screen, users can search for other users and communities and follow them, while they can also create their own community. In addition, they can have an overview of the latest contributions from the users they already follow.

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

Figure 20: Social tab

4.2 Mobile Application

Non-registered users

The only mobile app functionality that is available for non-registered users is to upload a sky photo that will be anonymized and saved in hackAIR. However, in order for users to see the air quality results from this photo, they should log in the application.

Figure 21: Uploading a sky photo for non-registered users

Registered users

Home page

By logging in the hackAIR mobile application, users can see a screen similar to the home page of the web application. Users can search for the city of their interest, and see the characterization of the current air quality, along with personalized recommendations and tips for improving the air quality.

Figure 22: Home page - mobile

By selecting the “History” button, users have access to historical air quality data for this specific city for a better comprehension of the air pollution evolution.

Figure 23: Historical data - mobile

On the bottom of the screen, there are four more tabs except from the first one which leads to the home screen.

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

Take a photo

On the second tab users can take and upload a sky photo or a photo of their cardboard sensor, following the instructions that are presented in the app.

Figure 24: Take a photo functionality - Mobile

Perception of air quality

On the third tab, users can submit their subjective perception on how they feel the current air quality in their location, as an additional information source for the other users.

Figure 25: Submit perception functionality - Mobile

Air quality map

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

The third tab contains the air quality map of hackAIR with all different sources of data. Users are able to select the map layers they want to view, by choosing the respective filters shown on the right of the screen.

Figure 26: Air quality map - Mobile

Profile

On the last tab, users can edit their profile, have an overview of their contributions, and see the specific measurements of their sensors.

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

Figure 27: Profile overview - Mobile

Upload mobile sensor measurements

A hackAIR functionality that is only available through the mobile application and not through the web platform is the ability for users to connect a mobile hackAIR sensor and send data to the hackAIR system. Users should have first set up a mobile sensor through the web platform as described in the relevant tutorial (<http://www.hackair.eu/hackair-mobile/>). Then they should switch on Bluetooth on their mobile device, return to the hackAIR app, choose the sensor that they have just created and simply start sending measurements to hackAIR as depicted below.

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

Figure 28: Connection with hackAIR mobile sensor - Mobile

5 Difficulties faced & lessons learnt

This section presents some of the difficulties that the development team faced since the beginning of the project and the actions that were taken in order to overcome them. These could be perceived as lessons learnt and useful tips to consider in future projects similar to hackAIR.

First thing to note is the integration of multiple different devices (mobile devices running different operating systems and having different native capabilities and configurations e.g. GPS, Camera, Arduino / Bluetooth / COTS sensors) and services that the team had to perform. The development team had to perform several integration tests in order to identify any issues with the integration of new services but also extend those tests to include specific issues that could not be foreseen from the beginning. For example, some specific Arduino platforms were sending wrong measurements to the hackAIR API due to low battery. As such problems were frequently reported by users outside the consortium, the development team needed to spend additional effort on issues like this, many times in communication with other project partners, in order to identify the problem and extend the existing integration tests in order to catch such cases in the future. On top of that, the development team paid a lot of effort in supporting hackAIR users for any issue needed through the project support email address. This was another task that was underestimated in the beginning of the project, but the consortium managed to handle it.

Another difficulty was that some hackAIR modules required too intensive resources (CPU, RAM) in order to run smoothly (e.g. the Image Analysis module). The development team decided to dedicate a new web server so that these modules can run on a separate machine that would have available resources, as needed, and migrate many of the hackAIR modules to the new web server. This also required additional testing (integration tests, functional tests etc.) to ensure that the migration was successful and that the Image Analysis module could work to its full capacity analyzing as many images as the other processes fed it with.

On another front, the development team realized that multiple steps were needed in order to work on the translations (export application texts to be translated into German and Norwegian, receive translations from the pilot partners and import them back to the apps) which was hard to cope with as translation suggestions kept coming. The team searched

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested hackAIR open platform

and suggested a better mechanism for handling the translations, which included a dynamic environment where partners would be able to enter the translations directly to a relational database and then these could be delivered to the mobile apps through the API.

hackAIR was planned to be an application that users would have to create a profile in order to use the mobile app. Initially we thought that if users did not have a profile on the platform they would miss on the experience especially on the mobile app and would also lower our statistics on contributed photos from users. It became evident however from the observed statistics, that users were discouraged when they downloaded the mobile app and realized they needed to create an account to use the application. Research proved that it is indeed a trend to release some of the app functionalities on mobile apps that people can use before deciding to create an account on the platform. Therefore, the team decided to tackle the problem and reengineered the workflow for the mobile apps, so that users can contribute sky photos even before they decide to create an account.

Additionally, as already mentioned in section 2.3, there were some mobile device-specific issues throughout the development process that came up that could not be reproduced by existing simulating software as they required capabilities from the mobile device (e.g. GPS, camera). The development team had to obtain specific mobile devices in order to reproduce those issues and setup a group of internal testers that would be able to reproduce and test those issues. For future attempts the team decided to use statistics on devices and operating systems that people use, in order to decide the deployment target and then decide more wisely on the technologies and frameworks that will be used for the development.

Finally, as regards the initial plan of the platform functionalities, the vision was to develop a platform with a lot of features and complexity. This was a bit ambitious plan that made it challenging for the development team to deliver a solution ready for use. It would be useful for future attempts that the team focuses first on the development of the most critical items that render the solution functional.

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